

PRESERVATION OF NATIONAL TRADITIONS AS THE BASIS OF CULTURAL IDENTITY

(based on the field data collected in the Karagandy region)

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Abstract. *The article examines the problem of preserving national traditions in the context of globalization and the rapid development of information technologies. It analyzes the role of traditions in shaping the cultural identity of individuals and society, as well as the significance of family, education, and cultural institutions in transmitting spiritual heritage to the younger generation. Special attention is given to the need for integrating national values into the educational process and public life. It is emphasized that under increasing global cultural influences, there is a growing risk of the erosion of traditional values, which requires the development of effective mechanisms for their preservation and promotion. The key directions considered include strengthening cultural and educational activities, developing nationally oriented education, and supporting intergenerational continuity.*

Key words: *national traditions, cultural identity, society, preservation, integration of new trends*

Introduction

In the modern world, globalization processes have a significant impact on people's culture and way of life. Technological advances, the rapid spread of mass culture, and changing social values are leading to the gradual loss of national characteristics. Under these circumstances, the issue of preserving traditions as a crucial element of a nation's cultural heritage is particularly pressing. Traditions are the spiritual foundation of society, reflecting the historical experience, worldview, moral values, and way of life of a people. They are passed down from generation to generation and ensure the continuity of cultural development. Preserving traditions helps strengthen national identity and foster respect for the history and culture of one's country.

Traditions serve an important social and educational function. They foster a sense of belonging to one's people and help preserve moral norms and cultural values. Traditions transmit knowledge of language, art, customs, rituals, and family values. National traditions contribute to the spiritual development of the individual. They instill respect for elders, a sense of responsibility, patriotism, and tolerance. It is through traditions that society preserves its uniqueness and cultural diversity. Furthermore, traditions play an important role in strengthening family relationships. Family holidays, customs, and shared events bring generations together and help maintain the spiritual bond between family members.

One of the main problems of our time is the declining interest of young people in their national culture. Many young people are more oriented toward foreign cultural models than toward the traditions of their own people. This is due to the influence of social media, the internet, and popular culture. Another problem is urbanization and changing lifestyles. In large cities, many national customs are gradually being lost, and traditional forms of communication are being replaced by digital communications. Another important problem is the declining use of the native language, which is the most important bearer of a nation's cultural values and traditions.

Studying this issue is important for several reasons. First, the decline in youth interest in national culture is linked to the formation of cultural identity, as national culture ensures the preservation of a system of values, historical memory, and a sense of belonging to one's people, and its weakening can lead to the erosion of cultural identity. Second, the influence of globalization, social

media, and popular culture increases the younger generation's orientation toward external cultural models, making it relevant to study the impact of the digital environment on the cultural preferences and behavior of young people. Third, urbanization and lifestyle changes are contributing to the gradual loss of traditional forms of communication, customs, and rituals, which negatively impacts the intergenerational transmission of cultural experience. Furthermore, the decline in the use of the native language is a serious problem, as language is the primary bearer of national values, traditions, and worldview, and its weakening can lead to a decrease in the cultural stability of society. Therefore, studying this issue allows us to identify current trends in cultural change among young people and develop effective educational and social measures to preserve national identity.

The preservation of national traditions in the context of globalization is widely recognized as an important interdisciplinary issue in sociology, cultural studies, and education. Scholars emphasize that traditions serve as a foundation of cultural identity, ensuring continuity between generations and maintaining collective historical memory. National identity is an integrative quality that fosters unity among citizens, transcending ethnic, political, or religious differences. It encompasses internal freedom, respect for government, love for the Motherland, and the ability to engage in positive interpersonal relationships [1]. According to Zhexembayeva et al. national identity continues to play a significant role in individuals' self-determination even under the conditions of globalization. It underlines the importance of developing strategies that take into account socio-cultural contexts to support and strengthen national identity. In this regard, the preservation of traditions is viewed as a key foundation for maintaining cultural identity and ensuring historical continuity within society [2]. Educational research highlights the crucial role of formal education in transmitting cultural values and preserving national heritage [3]. UNESCO emphasizes that education systems should integrate cultural content, including history, literature, folklore, and arts, to strengthen students' sense of identity and belonging. Similarly, Banks argues that multicultural and culturally responsive education contributes to both identity preservation and intercultural understanding [4]. Family and community are also considered primary agents of cultural transmission, as they provide the first social environment in which individuals acquire traditions, language, and values

Recent studies focus on the role of digital technologies and cultural institutions in safeguarding intangible cultural heritage. Digitalization facilitates the documentation and sharing of cultural heritage through online archives and multimedia platforms, enhancing accessibility and preserving endangered traditions. This transformation allows for broader reach and engagement with diverse audiences, reshaping cultural practices and values globally [5]. Digital implementation is essential for disseminating architectural and archaeological Cultural Heritage, offering opportunities through digital repositories and three-dimensional platforms, while emphasizing the importance of selecting appropriate tools considering their strengths and weaknesses in documentation [6]. Overall, the literature suggests that effective preservation of traditions requires a coordinated effort between family, education, cultural institutions, and the state, while also adapting traditions to contemporary social realities.

Materials and Methods

The study employed empirical data collected through semi-structured interviews with local residents of the Karaganda region. The sample also included repatriates, which enabled the researchers to obtain more diverse and multidimensional perspectives on the issue under investigation, taking into account different cultural and migration-related contexts. Overall,

6 respondents participated in the interview. A content analysis was conducted based on the respondents' answers to a number of key thematic questions, including:

- attitudes toward national culture and traditions;
- perceptions of cultural identity among young people;
- the influence of globalization and digital technologies on cultural values;
- the role of education and family in preserving national heritage;
- challenges related to cultural adaptation and integration;
- personal experiences and opinions regarding intercultural communication and social change.

Results and discussions

The aim of this research was to identify the current situation and conditions of preserving national traditions currently and what factors influence their development. The revealed data are demonstrated in the following table.

Table 1 Content analysis on the data revealed from respondents

Thematic category	Interview Question	Responses from Participants	Interpretation
National culture and traditions	What does national culture mean to you?	“It is an important part of our identity”; “Traditions unite people”; “Young people are losing interest in traditions”	Cultural identity; preservation of traditions; cultural decline
Cultural identity among youth	How do young people relate to national culture today?	“Youth are more influenced by Western culture”; “Some young people respect traditions”; “Social media changes their values”	Globalization influence; generational differences
Role of family	What role does the family play in preserving culture?	“Parents teach traditions”; “Grandparents preserve language and customs”; “Families celebrate national holidays together”	Families support
Education	How can education support national heritage?	“Schools should teach more about traditions”; “Universities should organize cultural events”; “Language learning is important”	Education influence
Globalization and digitalization	How do globalization and digital technologies affect culture?	“Technology helps spread culture”; “Global media weakens traditions”; “Youth spend more time online than with family”	Digital influence; cultural transformation
Migration and repatriation experiences	What challenges do repatriates face in adaptation?	“Language barriers”; “Difficulty integrating into society”; “Strong desire to preserve ethnic identity”	Adaptation challenges; identity preservation
Intercultural communication	How do different cultures interact in society?	“Cultural diversity enriches society”; “There are misunderstandings”	Multiculturalism; social integration

		between generations”; “Tolerance is important”	
Preservation of heritage	What should be done to preserve national heritage?	Organize cultural festivals”; “Promote traditional music and art”; “Support youth participation in cultural activities”	Cultural preservation

The findings of the content analysis demonstrate that national culture continues to play a significant role in shaping personal and collective identity among the respondents. Most participants emphasized that traditions, language, and cultural values remain important elements of social cohesion and intergenerational continuity. At the same time, the study revealed growing concerns regarding the declining interest of younger generations in national customs and traditional practices. Respondents frequently associated this tendency with the increasing influence of globalization, Western culture, and digital media, which transform value systems and everyday lifestyles.

The results also underline the important role of family and educational institutions in preserving cultural heritage. Participants noted that parents and grandparents serve as the primary transmitters of traditions, language, and national values, while schools and universities are expected to strengthen cultural awareness through educational programs and extracurricular activities. Furthermore, the inclusion of repatriates in the study provided additional perspectives on cultural adaptation and identity preservation. Their experiences highlighted both the difficulties of social integration and the strong motivation to maintain ethnic and cultural belonging. Overall, the findings suggest that intercultural communication, family influence, and educational support remain key factors in sustaining national identity within the context of contemporary globalization and social change.

Conclusion

The preservation of traditions requires active participation from the family, school, state, and society. First and foremost, the family plays a crucial role, as it is within the family that a child is initially introduced to the culture of their people, national customs, and values. The education system should also contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage. It is necessary to include materials on national history, literature, arts, folklore, and traditions in the educational process. The organization of cultural events, festivals, exhibitions, and thematic lessons helps to develop students’ interest in national culture. Cultural centers, museums, and libraries also play a significant role, as they promote folk art, crafts, and traditional rituals.

Modern technologies can likewise be effectively used for preserving cultural heritage. The creation of digital archives, educational platforms, and multimedia projects enables the dissemination of knowledge about traditions among young people. Thus, the preservation of traditions is an important condition for the spiritual and cultural development of society. National traditions help maintain the historical memory of a people, strengthen cultural identity, and ensure intergenerational continuity. In the context of globalization, fostering respect for national culture and spiritual values becomes particularly significant. Effective preservation of traditions is possible only through the joint efforts of the family, educational institutions, cultural organizations, and the state. It is important not only to preserve traditions but also to adapt them to contemporary conditions, making them a meaningful part of young people’s lives.

REFERENCES

1. Ekhaeva, R. M., Arskieva, Z. A., & Vershitsky, A. (2024). Formation of national identity as the basis of intercultural communication. *SHS Web of Conferences*, 195, 05003. <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/202419505003>
2. Zhexembekova, U., Kalashnikova, N., & Poujol, C. (2025). The problem of national identity in the context of increasing globalization. *Gosudarstvennoe Upravlenie i Gosudarstvennaâ Služba*. <https://doi.org/10.52123/1994-2370-2025-1643>
3. UNESCO. (2017). *Safeguarding Intangible Cultural Heritage*. Paris: UNESCO.
4. Banks, J. A. (2015). *Cultural Diversity and Education*. Routledge.
5. Tillayeva, G. (2025). The Impact of Digitalization on Cultural Practices and Values. *International Journal of Law and Policy*, 3(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.59022/ijlp.263>
6. Cimadomo, G. (2013). Documentation and dissemination of Cultural Heritage: Current solutions and considerations about its digital implementation. *Digital Heritage International Congress*, 555–562. <https://doi.org/10.1109/DIGITALHERITAGE.2013.6743796>

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